
Institutional Development and the Dynamics of Power Through Time

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Abstract

Explanations of institutional reproduction and change processes often rely on two causal pathways: on one hand, the contextual conditions in which particular power structures are formed and stabilized over time; on the other, the (often unintended) consequences of the strategies of various actors involved in the struggle over the distribution of institutional resources (Collier & Munck, 2022; Mahoney & Thelen, 2010).

The underlying debate stems from the distinction between exogenous and endogenous dynamics of institutional structuring and change. From Tilly's relational-processual perspective, this distinction is less relevant, as causation is attributed to the interaction among actors, strategies, and contextual configurations in which resource distribution and production are contested and continuously reconfigured. This approach aligns with exchange theory models derived from network analysis, where the stabilization of relational structures results from the formation of commitments around resource mobilization. These, in turn, produce power effects and establish differences in terms of power, prestige, and privilege (Cook, 2003).

A stabilized exchange network constrains behavior, thus constituting an institution. Its formation and change result from contingent commitments shaped by the mobilization of resources, where participants may turn to alternative sources. Therefore, networks should not be seen as determining structures, but rather as the conditions within which interactions occur. Time is thus crucial: specific changes take place within historically situated conditions.

Building on these assumptions, we propose examining institutional formation and change through network analysis of actors, organizations, and events over time. The objective is to identify repeated interactions that suggest relatively stabilized resource exchanges, pointing to the formation of commitments that define the network, while changes in interaction signal weakening or transformation. We draw on data from a previous study on the trajectories of two landmark institutions of Mexican democracy: the electoral body and the transparency institute, from 1989 to 2021, encompassing phases of creation, consolidation, and institutional change.

Following the historical method tradition, we emphasize identifying critical junctures, as these moments often diversify options for resource mobilization, potentially leading to exchange networks that persist over time. Alternatively, such junctures may discourage commitment formation due to resource diversification, making institutional stabilization or change

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more a result of actor strategies.

Data and Methods

We constructed a bipartite network based on co-participation of individuals in organizations and events related to the evolution of Mexico's electoral and transparency institutions. Events were selected for their relevance in episodes of institutional building, conflict, and reform, and organizations were chosen based on contextual importance. The dataset includes 3,000 nodes and 5,000 edges-individuals (politicians, academics, activists, civil society members) on one side, and institutions/events where they co-participated on the other.

To examine activity systems throughout these institutions' trajectories, we used Gephi and the Leiden algorithm to detect communities. We organized the network on a temporal axis according to the year of node appearance (Fig. 1).

A processual interpretation of the graph layout suggests long-term activity systems (orange and green clusters) that converge with the emergence of two others (blue and pink). The long-term processes align with political liberalization, while the middle clusters reflect relationships stemming from new institutions like the electoral and transparency bodies. A third phase shows these communities fading and a new dominant one (light blue) emerging, coinciding with reforms to both institutions in a context of multiparty consensus.

The layout reflects historical context, yet raises questions about the communities' role in network formation and change. If convergence indicates institutionalization, the subsequent dissolution of nodes and links challenges linear interpretations. Long-term processes appear to persist across formation, structuring, and change phases.

In the second phase of analysis, we examined intra- and inter-community link activity over time, using a more granular partition (Glay algorithm in Cytoscape). We identified 26 subgroups and calculated the modal internal relations as indicators of latent emergence, allowing us to define nine time periods based on subgraph activity.

For each period, we counted inter-community links as an indicator of their importance in resource exchange. A higher share of such links suggests greater community influence, whether as resource providers or receivers. Figure 3 presents a heatmap showing the proportion of links developed by each community relative to the possible total for each period.

This heatmap (fig 2) reveals dynamic processes across time, led by seven prominent communities. As in Graph 1, communities five and twelve maintain long-term activity. Community one shows a steady rise until t7, while community nine displays sustained, declining relevance until t6. Three others peak in specific periods: nineteen in t2, eighteen in t8, and four in t8-t9.

The analysis of the link density of the communities towards the outside, combined with their coincidence in time periods, reveals three processes:

- Between t1 and t3, four communities coincide: nineteen, nine, twelve, and one. In this period, which goes from 1989 to 1994, we identify the juncture of reforms through which the electoral institute was created and became an independent body, led by figures recognized as citizens. Community twelve contains this institutional body, and we infer that it gained power through interaction with communities one and nine, which contain the electoral body and the hegemonic party (PRI), which together concentrate 13% of all accumulated relations from the periods. In t2, the activity of community nineteen intensifies; it contains the *Coloquio de Invierno*, an intellectual forum organized by the magazine *Vuelta* and the company *Televisa* to analyze the democratic transition in Mexico. During t2, the four overlapping communities concentrate 53% of the inter-subgraph relations of the entire network.
- Between t4 and t7, there is an almost constant increase in the external activity of

community one; a sustained decrease in community nine; and the activation of community five. The latter is representative of the transparency institute and relevant actors from civil society organizations that are influential in the national political arena. The period, which runs from 1994 to 2010, encompasses increasing political liberalization, the last electoral reform, the alternation in the executive, and the emergence of new accountability institutions, including the transparency body. In t6, which spans from 2000 to 2004, communities nine, five, and one coincide, concentrating 43% of the network's links.

- Between t8 and t9, we observe the peak of external activity of communities four and eighteen - the former made up of protagonists from civil society organizations and research centers, among which the Legal Research Institute of the UNAM stands out; the latter contains the new electoral body, the INE. In t8, which covers the period from 2011 to 2016, the appearance of these new communities coincides with community five, together accounting for 50% of the network's links in that period. In t9, which goes from 2016 to 2021, only communities four and five develop 37% of the established relationships among all active communities.

Viewing these communities as systems, the interactional perspective challenges abrupt historical cuts and weakens the explanatory power of critical junctures or path dependence. Instead, what we observe is past-dependency through systems of resource transfer among communities. The stabilization of the network in t4-t7, led by communities 5 and 1, depends on earlier interactions forged by communities 9, 1, 12, and 19. Similarly, change from t8 onward, marked by communities 4 and 18, emerges from prior dynamics led by communities 1 and 5 (fig 3).

Conclusions

Network analysis enables the study of institutional formation and change through the lens of interactive processes among actors, their strategies, and contextual configurations. Mapping individuals, events, and organizations revealed a structure suitable for processual analysis using historical community detection-both in relational distribution over time and intra- and inter-community activity.

Modal values of internal community links align with their latent emergence and historical context. Inter-community links were strong indicators of relevance in the network's resource exchange processes. We identified three major processes explaining the formation, stabilization, and transformation of the networks tied to Mexico's landmark democratic institutions. By examining community connectivity and its interaction with historical context, we observe system dynamics that reflect past-dependency in institutional formation and change. This is not a matter of path dependence in the traditional sense of historical rule entrenchment, but of interaction systems that hypothetically transfer resources over time.

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Keywords: Process tracing, political history, institutional building, past dependence